

TESREMIN - CONTROLLING A TESLA COIL USING A THEREMIN

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ABSTRACT

A Theremin is an electronic musical instrument with two antennas that produces an electromagnetic field and - without any physical contact – the instrument detects hand movements, measuring their distance and translating them into sound. A Tesla Coil is an electronic device that produces high voltage lightning bolts and can also be used to play music (although this is not its original purpose). With the *Tesremin* we combine the concept of a Theremin and the Tesla Coil as a device to form a new digital musical instrument (DMI). We devised a strategy to design, develop and evaluate a *Tesremin* prototype. The final prototype is constructed using a Raspberry Pi 5 and two ultrasonic sensors, which generates square waves to control a Tesla Coil. Afterwards, an evaluation with a musician is conducted to assess the instrument’s technical usability and its musical appeal. During the evaluation, the musician tested the *Tesremin* extensively. In terms of appeal, the evaluation revealed a significant amount of excitement and curiosity toward the instrument. In terms of usability, the instrument was easy to play, but was held back by a noticeable delay between hand movements and corresponding pitch changes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Theremin is an electronic instrument invented by Léon Theremin during the 1920s and patented in 1928. [1] It consists of two antennas, one vertical and straight and the other horizontal and ring-shaped. The vertical antenna controls the pitch and the ring-shaped antenna controls the volume of the produced sound. The Theremin is the first known electronic instrument to be played without physical contact of the body. Instead, the player controls it by moving their hands near the antennas, adjusting the frequency and amplitude based on their distance. The antennas create an electromagnetic field, with the hands serving as the capacitors. Thus, by moving in range of the field, oscillations are generated and a sound is audible. These oscillations cannot be produced by other musical instruments – the music is therefore unique. [2] Musicians can use this technological method and interaction technique to express themselves musically in a unique way, though it affords training to play, due to the absence of note visualization

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or any other aid for finding the correct pitch. Thus, the Theremin requires players to rely solely on their ear and muscle memory to play the correct notes. Due to these factors, the Theremin is generally regarded as one of the hardest instruments to master. [3]

The Tesla Coil, invented by Nikola Tesla in 1914 [4], is a device that produces high voltage for the purpose of creating artificial lightning bolts. This is achieved by utilizing a primary coil and a secondary coil. By coupling them together, they form a transformer — a device capable of increasing or decreasing voltage. Using this transformer, high voltages are used to produce lightning bolts. [5] Each of these generated lightning bolts produces a unique sound reminiscent of regular electrical discharge. While not Teslas original intention, these lightning bolts may be modulated to produce deliberate sounds and even musical pieces.

This paper seeks to combine these two devices to form a new Digital Musical Instrument (DMI) prototype called the *Tesremin*, a word created from *Tesla* and *Theremin*. The *Tesremin* is created to explore the potential of a Tesla Coil as an audio output device and to utilize ultrasonic sensors as a Theremin instrument. By using any kind of musical interface (in our case a self-built Theremin consisting of ultrasonic sensors) as an input device and a Tesla Coil as the audio output device, we can successfully achieve this goal.

In the remainder of this paper, we will discuss related work, our devised methodology, the implementation of the *Tesremin*, an evaluation conducted with a hobby musician, and a discussion of both the evaluation and the paper as a whole, followed by a conclusion.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 From the Theremin to a Digital Musical Instrument

The Theremin underwent numerous design iterations before evolving into the instrument we know today. It was invented in 1920 by Léon Theremin and is considered one of the hardest instruments to master. The two antennas to control the sound require precise hand movements, as any slight reposition causes changes to the pitch or volume. [3]

The difficulty in mastering the Theremin is demonstrated by Johnson et al. [6]. The primary objective of this work was to develop a tool that aids aspiring *thereminists* (a term informally used in the Theremin online community to describe Theremin players) in their practice. This is achieved by positioning a real Theremin in front of a player

and building a VR environment, in which a simulated Theremin is shown at the same 3D space as the physical device. By wearing a VR headset, the player can view visual cues for notes in the virtual space while playing an actual Theremin. This mixed reality approach allows for rapid skill development and more precise control during play.

In the 1990s and early 2000s, the Theremin saw a resurgence in popularity. [7] As microcontrollers, like Arduinos, became widely available for private consumers, hardware enthusiasts began building their own versions of the instrument using a variety of materials and components. Building a Theremin using ultrasonic sensors is especially well documented and a popular starting point for beginners interested in electronics. Ultrasonic sensors operate by emitting an ultrasonic signal and measuring the time it takes for the signal to bounce back. The longer it takes, the further an object (i.e. a player's hand) is away. Hanindhito et al. [8] implemented a Theremin using CORDIC (Coordinate Rotation Digital Computer), which is a digital circuit that can be used to compute several common mathematical transcendental functions with only basic hardware requirements, as well as several circuits and similar ultrasonic sensors.

Geiger et al. [9] describe their design of two Theremin-based Musical Interfaces, namely a Nintendo Wii controller and a hand tracking device. In their formal evaluation they mainly focus on usability and manageability, but also take into account the excitement and curiosity of the evaluators towards a particular device. Their work can help us define desirable characteristics of Musical Interfaces and craft a suitable evaluation according to them.

Further modern sensor-based versions that adapt the concept of a Theremin, include a paper describing a virtual Theremin for accompanying film scenes [10], a paper describing a technique to measure body movement using a Theremin [11] and a Theremin Textural Expander [12].

2.2 Tesla Coil: An electronic innovation for musical purposes

Tesla [4] patented an apparatus, that was later termed the Tesla Coil, with which it was possible to transmit electrical energy. It is designed using a self-resonant secondary coil in the form of a tower as well as a primary coil at the side.

Later, researchers such as Jana et al. [5] discussed the implementation of spark-gap based Tesla Coils. A spark gap functions by using a transformer to reach high voltage until eventually an arc forms in the gap. This arc then allows current to flow through. Older Tesla Coil models implement a spark gap. The spark gap allows the current in the coil to be switched on or off quickly. A voltage is built up on several opposing spheres. Air becomes conductive at 1000 V/mm, thus it is possible to adjust the breakdown voltage over the distance of the spheres. If the spheres are close to each other, the coil can be supplied with electricity more frequently. Conversely, if the spheres were further apart, the frequency would be lower. Since large currents are at work, the construction of spark gaps is a delicate process – oxides quickly accumulate or melt. Unfortunately,

modulating the frequency of the current was exceedingly difficult. It was only through the development of high-performance switches made of semiconductors that it was possible to modulate switching on and off. It is important to mention that exactly one flash is created by a single switching on/off. By using semiconductors, it is possible to "only" change the frequency of the flashes. If the amount of current is changed at the primary coil, the flash strength (the intensity or volume) may be changed.

The next step of innovation saw the invention of Solid State Tesla Coils (SSTC) as an alternative to spark-gap Tesla Coils. Soleyman et al. [13] used semiconductor transistors (MOSFET) for this task. As a result, SSTCs offer a wide range of potential applications and can be designed to be much smaller. This paper mainly utilizes SSTCs due to ease of handling and Bluetooth capabilities.

As Tanwar et al. [14] put it, musical SSTCs are a relatively new research topic, and only a small number of papers have been published to date. Thus, this paper hopes to further the knowledge of such systems as well as their versatility. As described by Tanwar et al., a Tesla Coil requires square waves as input data. This is because Tesla Coils are not built to handle continuous signals such as common sine waves, due to a Tesla Coil only being either turned on or off. It is impossible to create continuous lightning bolts using a Tesla Coil, thus it is necessary to generate lightning in quick succession. To an observer, the lightning appears to flash at different frequencies, as if each flash has its own pitch. But in reality, the flashes just happen at the rate set by the chosen frequency.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research follows a design approach, in which a new DMI prototype, the *Tesremin*, is designed, developed and evaluated. The goal is to explore the feasibility of using a Tesla Coil as an output device for any DMI. The focus is thus on the development of a functional interface that connects to and uses a Tesla Coil to form a DMI. By fully decoupling the ultrasonic-sensor-Theremins input handling from the Tesla Coils output interface, we want to also allow other interfaces to control the Tesla Coil.

During the development of the *Tesremin*, we went through three distinct iterations, each allowing us to enhance its usability, complexity, and performance. The first iteration we aim to explore involves completely separating the Theremin from the Tesla Coil interface. This would be achieved by using an Arduino to build the Theremin, while a Raspberry Pi would serve as the interface for controlling the Tesla Coil. This setup would theoretically allow us to control one or multiple Tesla Coils by connecting multiple Digital Musical Interfaces (DMIs) to the Raspberry Pi. In the second approach, we plan to correct previously made mistakes, this includes integrating the Theremin directly into the Raspberry Pi to reduce complexity and streamline communication with the Tesla Coil interface. Finally, in the third approach, we intend to use Sonic Pi, a music creation and performance tool, to control the Tesla Coil, replacing the previously used method which consisted of a Python script handling the conversion and audio output.

This would enable the generation of high-quality audio signals with minimal effort. By reflecting on this iterative process and the various approaches, we aim to determine which method is most technically effective for using these devices. Additionally, we seek to assess whether a musical instrument powered by a Tesla Coil is musically appealing to musicians.

After finalizing the *Tesremin* prototype, we conducted an evaluation with an expert musician with two main objectives: determining the usability of the *Tesremin* as a musical instrument and assessing the appeal of a Tesla Coil-based instrument, focusing on the excitement and curiosity expressed toward the *Tesremin*. This evaluation will therefore assess the capabilities of the *Tesremin* as a digital musical instrument.

During the implementation and the subsequent evaluation, two Tesla Coil variants were used. One SSTC Tesla Coil, namely the 10CM mini Tesla Coil by Wuhan Stark Technology Co.,Ltd.¹, as well as non-SSTC Tesla Coil.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Initial Exploration

For our first prototype, we used an Arduino with two ultrasonic sensors, a Raspberry Pi 5 running Python code, Open Sound Control (OSC)² messaging and the Tesla Coil 10CM mini.

Separating the Arduino-Theremin from the Raspberry Pi (RPi) server allowed multiple musical interfaces, similar to the Arduino-Theremin, to interact with the RPi. This setup would enable the RPi to control multiple Tesla coils and instruments simultaneously.

We connected the two ultrasonic sensors to the Arduino, where they measured the distance to the operator's hands. The measured distance was then used to calculate frequency and amplitude, respectively. The Arduino transmitted these calculated values to the Raspberry Pi via OSC messaging.

The RPi would be used as a server that receives OSC messages from one or many DMIs (i.e. the Arduino) and would then generate a square wave signal using the received frequency and amplitude. The generated square wave was then output via an audio stream using the Sounddevice Python library.³ The RPi would then be connected to the Tesla Coil either by Bluetooth or by cable (3.5mm, USB etc.).

4.1.1 Findings

The initial exploration revealed two technical problems: Firstly, OSC messaging between the two systems requires both devices to be connected to the same network. This renders a standard Arduino unusable, as it does not support WiFi capabilities. This could be circumvented by either using an Arduino WiFi shield, which is a WiFi hardware extension for Arduino, or discarding the Arduino entirely

Figure 1. Component Wiring

and using an ESP 32, which is similar to an Arduino but with built-in WiFi and Bluetooth support.

Secondly, the reliance of OSC in a network connection could prove detrimental in the case of a network failure as this would render the entire system inoperative until the connection is restored. This introduces robustness and reliability issues, making the system undesirable.

Due to these factors, signal handling, frequency and amplitude conversion, and square wave generation were not implemented in this exploration, as a better solution needed to be found first. Thus the instrument was not functional at this stage.

4.2 Proof-of-Concept

Due to the restrictions we observed during the technical exploration using an Arduino and OSC messaging, we decided to solely use a Raspberry Pi to create a proof-of-concept. Thus the proof-of-concept involved the utilization of the RPi's GPIO pins to integrate the Theremin directly into the RPi. This reduced complexity and made the *Tesremin* less error-prone by relying solely on internal messaging within a single device.

The entire workflow, from signal handling to square wave conversion and audio output, was implemented in Python. This choice streamlined the process by eliminating the need for data transfer between multiple systems, which might cause delay, while leveraging Python's extensive capabilities.

Since the Raspberry Pi 5 operates at 3.3 volts [15], while the ultrasonic sensors require 5 volts, a voltage level conversion is necessary. This is achieved using resistors to convert the returning sensor voltage to 3.3 volts, preventing potential damage to the RPi from frequent usage. The wiring of the components is shown in Figure 1, with the RPi on the left, the breadboard in the middle and two ultrasonic sensors on the right. The black wire is ground, the red wire 5V and the blue and green wires are GPIO slots for echo and trigger of the sensors. Six 1K ohm resistors are used to convert 5V to 3.3V.

The Python library `gpiozero`⁴ is used to communicate with the sensors. By implementing a distance limitation of 50 cm for the sensors, the received values are between 0

¹ <https://fcc.report/FCC-ID/2BGJC-WHSTKTC10MINI/>

² <https://pypi.org/project/python-osc/>

³ <https://python-sounddevice.readthedocs.io/en/0.5.1/>

⁴ <https://gpiozero.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

and 0.5. These two distance values needed to be processed into the required amplitude data. The amplitude data is multiplied by a value of 2, due to regular amplitude values being between 0 (min) and 1 (max).

4.2.1 Mathematical Approach to Frequency Data Conversion

The frequency sensor data, however, requires a more sophisticated approach to be converted into usable frequencies. As stated in the work of van Uven [16], frequency is perceived logarithmically. This means that the difference between 500Hz and 1000Hz is perceived the same as the difference between 1000Hz and 2000Hz. In music theory, both would represent one octave. It is thus impossible to convert the distance data (0 - 0.5) to logical frequencies using an arbitrary number (e.g. multiplying by 1000). Due to this, a formula is needed to map the distance data to the corresponding frequency. This formula is a logarithmic interpolation to receive the desired frequency. To demonstrate how to arrive at this final equation, we must first examine the following Equation (1), which is the formula for linear interpolation between two values, a and b and for a parameter t ranging from 0 to 1. a is the start value, b is the end value and t the interpolation factor.

$$y = a + t * (b - a) \quad (1)$$

Due to t being normalized, this can be transformed into logarithmic interpolation by taking the logarithm of a and b , shown in Equation (2).

$$\log(freq) = \log(a) + t * (\log(b) - \log(a)) \quad (2)$$

Finally, the calculated $\log(freq)$ value requires to be transformed back into linear space, shown in Equation (3).

$$freq = e^{\log(freq)} \quad (3)$$

After the conversion of the distance data to sensible values, the converted frequency and amplitude is used to generate square waves. This is achieved using the `signal.square()` method from the python library SciPy⁵. `signal.square` requires the amplitude, frequency, sample rate (by default 44100) as well as a time array t as input and returns an array containing the square waveform.

Lastly, the generated square wave is output using an output stream and audio callback from the Python library `sounddevice`⁶. In the audio callback method, an out-data array is created using the square wave as data.

4.2.2 Findings

The proof-of-concept presented fewer issues compared to the initial exploration. The signal handling, distance measuring, frequency and amplitude conversion, and square wave generation were implemented correctly and yielded accurate results.

However, Python's audio output was not suitable for this type of continuous signal generation. Due to the

⁵ <https://scipy.org/>

⁶ <https://python-sounddevice.readthedocs.io/en/0.5.1/>

sheer number of measurements, the audio output was overloaded. Faultless and smooth transitioning between different signals was especially challenging. Thus the output using Python was discarded and a better suited alternative was sought.

4.3 Final prototype

4.3.1 Overall concept

To improve the square wave conversion as well as the continuous audio output, the music creation application Sonic Pi was chosen. Due to its compatibility with an RPi, ease of use, and suitability for live performances, it proved to be an ideal choice.

Sonic Pi is a program created by Sam Aaron [17] and his team for the purpose of live music performances and music creation. It utilizes the Ruby programming language. Sonic Pi has a variety of built-in features for sound and signal manipulation as well as the capability of changing code at runtime for an optimal live performance experience. Sonic Pi will thus replace the `sounddevice` and `SciPy` Python libraries and handle the conversion to square waves as well as the audio output.

4.3.2 Communication and Square Wave generation

After generating sensible frequency and amplitude data using our Python script, the data is sent to Sonic Pi using OSC. Since Sonic Pi and the Python script run on the same Raspberry Pi, OSC messages can be sent locally, eliminating the need for a network connection and by extension, any network-related errors. Messages can also be sent within the network, enabling other instruments to interact with the same Raspberry Pi (RPI) as originally intended.

Upon receiving the OSC message, Sonic Pi converts the received frequency to the corresponding MIDI note (using the inbuilt method `Hz_to_midi()`), which is needed for Sonic Pi output. Sonic Pi then uses a synth, created on runtime start, to continuously output sound, overwriting the previous output with any newly received data. By using the `:square` keyword when creating the synth, the output will automatically be converted to square wave signals. The finished Sonic Pi code can be found in Figure 2. It displays the synth creation, OSC message handling as well as the midi Note creation and overwriting of the synth with newly received data.

To summarize the workflow: first, the sensors detect a signal. Then the distance measured is converted to sensible amplitude and frequency data, which is then sent to Sonic Pi using OSC messaging. In Sonic Pi, the frequency is converted to a Midi note and a square wave synth is created. Lastly, the audio is output using an audio device (i.e. a Tesla Coil). This workflow can also be viewed in Figure 3.

4.3.3 Prototype Casing and Component Housing

Until this point, the various components, such as the Raspberry Pi and wiring, were loose. A casing was introduced to securely house and organize them while also allowing the instrument to be transported and played in different locations. To accomplish this without great effort and costs,

```

1 teslaSynthOutput = synth :square, note: 0, amp: 0, cutoff: 130,
2   release: 0, sustain: 1000000, slide: 0.1
3
4 live_loop :listen do
5   use_real_time
6   freq, amp = sync "/osc*/sound"
7   if freq > 0
8     midiNote = hz_to_midi(freq)
9     control teslaSynthOutput, note: midiNote, amp: amp
10  else
11    control teslaSynthOutput, note: 0, amp: 0
12  end
13 end
14

```

Figure 2. Sonic Pi ruby code which handles the OSC message receiving and Hz to MIDI conversion as well as the output.

Figure 3. System architecture and communication of components

a plastic container was retrofitted to house the components and serve as a proof-of-concept for the instrument. Holes were drilled into the lid to fit the ultrasonic sensors from the inside. The Raspberry Pi as well as the rest of the wiring components were attached to the bottom inside using a cardboard plate, adhesives and cable ties. Holes were drilled into the side of the container to access the USB ports of the RPi. Finally, a screen was attached to the back of the container from the outside and connected to the RPi, allowing for interaction and the initiation of necessary scripts. This prototype can be viewed in Figure 4, which shows the front view of the box with the RPi, the breadboard, the wiring as well as the two ultrasonic sensors on the lid visible, the back view with the monitor visible and the side view with the RPi positioned in a way to access the USB ports from the outside.

The source code of the project may be found on Gitlab.⁷ Additionally, a short Demo video can be found on Youtube.⁸

4.3.4 Findings

While trying out the *Tesremin* for the first time, we noticed that the frequency sensor responds correctly to hand movements and generates frequency accordingly, however

⁷ <https://git01lab.cs.univie.ac.at/alexanderg86/tesremin.git>

⁸ <https://youtu.be/KIaDfdMeryE>

the amplitude sensor did not correctly change the volume of the Tesla Coil 10 mini. With further testing of the amplitude sensor, we discovered that this type of Tesla Coil does not support amplitude modulation. This is apparently common for some SSTC variants. This includes the Tesla Coil 10 mini used in this research. In these coils, amplitude changes instead result in frequency shifts, effectively providing two distinct methods for pitch modulation. Another Tesla Coil used in this research has exhibited the ability to allow amplitude shifts using software. This information is not readily apparent for any Tesla Coil and thus needs to be tested for each Coil. Using the other coil yielded better results, as it allowed for amplitude adjustments.

Another persistent issue is a noticeable delay between the player's hand movements and the resulting pitch change. This might be caused by the various conversion and transmission steps, with Bluetooth and the ultrasonic sensors suspected to be mainly responsible.

5. EVALUATION

5.1 Setting

An evaluation was conducted with the assistance of a hobby musician, who has been playing the piano and saxophone since childhood, but has no prior experience with a Theremin, which is a recognized limitation. The goal

Figure 4. *Tesremin* prototype.

of the evaluation was to assess the instrument’s technical usability and its ability to evoke musical interest, with a particular focus on the enjoyment of playing. The evaluation took place at the musician’s home, with two residents observing. The test included 2 tasks, lasted 20 minutes and was documented in written notes.

The first task was conducted using the *Tesremin* prototype but using a Bluetooth speaker as an output device instead of a Tesla Coil. This was done to assess the difference of controlling regular speakers and a Tesla Coil. First, the musician was asked to set up the prototype to evaluate its ease of use. Following this, they were instructed to play a musical scale, perform vibrato, attempt a piece of their choice, and improvise. These tasks were designed to assess both the usability and musical potential of the instrument.

The second task was conducted using the *Tesremin* prototype with the Tesla Coil 10 mini as an output device. The musician first tested this constellation using both sensors (frequency and amplitude). Afterwards, the amplitude value was fixed at a constant value of 1 and only the frequency sensor was used to control the coil. This adjustment was made because volume control is not inherently possible on this particular Tesla Coil, and maintaining a constant value of 1 produced better results. This is not the case with other Tesla Coils tested, but seems to be the case for some SSTC devices. The musician was then asked to complete the same tasks as previously described.

5.2 Results

Both tests yielded similar results, with the musician noticing the previously discussed delay between hand movements and audible output. He estimated it to be around 0.7 seconds. According to the musician, while this delay is not ideal and affects playability, it is not uncommon in certain

other instruments such as some synthesizers. As a result, the musician considered the instrument impractical rather than unusable, noting that it would take considerable time to master and lacked the responsiveness needed for quick pitch changes, such as those required for vibrato.

After the second task, the musician observed that the absence of amplitude control was not ideal, as volume changes are crucial for adding dynamics to the music.

The musician also suggested the idea of incorporating a foot-operated button switch to stop the sensor input when pressed. This would allow the performer to cut off certain notes, adding an extra layer of control and depth to the performance.

Despite these points of criticism, the musician was fascinated by the *Tesremin*. The ability to utilize lightning bolts for musical purposes was especially intriguing to the musician. In his view, the sound produced by the lightning bolts was distinctive, yet subtly evocative of sci-fi-themed music. The musician also praised the comfort and ease of use when playing the *Tesremin*. Overall, he described the experience as fun, exciting and educational, and expressed that the *Tesremin* holds great potential as a niche instrument, provided the existing flaws are addressed.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Reflection on the Evaluation

Geiger et al. [9] described their evaluation in great detail, with a specific focus on usability as well as the excitement and curiosity generated by a particular device. Although our evaluation was limited to a single evaluator, we focused on the excitement and curiosity it generated—similar to the approach of Geiger et al.—to assess both the usability of the *Tesremin* and its appeal to musicians.

6.1.1 Appeal

In terms of appeal, our evaluation revealed a significant amount of excitement and curiosity towards the instrument, as the musician repeatedly expressed his joy while playing as well as commending the interesting design. Especially memorable for the musician was the fact that lightning bolts were used to create sound, calling it an exhilarating feeling. The house residents, who served as a spontaneous audience, provided an opportunity to evaluate the enjoyment of listeners experiencing the *Tesremin*. They described it as a unique musical experience unlike anything they had seen before, finding it both interesting and fun to listen to. This highlights how an audience unfamiliar with Tesla Coil music may have never encountered such performances, making it a valuable and memorable experience. The long-term appeal of audience members has yet to be tested.

6.1.2 Usability

According to the musician, the *Tesremin* was relatively simple to setup and comfortable to play. Unlike instruments such as the piano or saxophone, where finger strength and accuracy are crucial, the *Tesremin*, just like a regular Theremin, only requires the player’s hands to be in

the air, without physical contact, making it a more intuitive and less physically demanding instrument to engage with.

However, the usability is compromised by the noticeable delay between hand movements and the corresponding sound generation. This delay made it difficult for the musician to play comfortably and led them to describe the instrument as impractical, though not impossible to play.

6.2 Reflecting on technical issues

The most significant obstacle to realizing the potential of the *Tesremin* is the noticeable delay. While the instrument remains playable despite this issue, the delay negatively impacts both usability and enjoyment. Throughout the implementation and testing phases, no reliable solution was found to effectively reduce the delay. This limitation should be acknowledged and, if possible, addressed in future work.

The ultrasonic sensors used, which were similarly used and discussed in the research by Hanindhito et al. [8] proved to be a suitable component, effectively fulfilling their intended purpose. However, there is a possibility that the ultrasonic sensors could be contributing to the delay, as some reports indicate that these types of sensors can result in slower input handling. Instead, opting for similar devices, such as time-of-flight sensors, may offer improved performance and reduce the latency.

Any further research and improvement of technical *Tesremin* aspects such as the delay, improved frequency reading, timbre etc. were out of scope for this paper and may be addressed in future works.

6.3 Reflecting on musical aspects

During the evaluation, the musician suggested incorporating a foot-operated button switch to temporarily disable the sensor input when pressed. This would allow for the intentional cutting off of certain notes and stopping continuous audio output when undesired. A similar foot-pedal solution was implemented in the research of Waldhör et al. [18] to address this exact issue. Their findings confirm that a foot pedal is a valid and effective solution, which could enhance the playability of the *Tesremin*.

6.4 The Tesla coil for musical purposes

Most scientific research on musical Tesla Coils focuses almost exclusively on the implementation and construction of the Tesla Coil itself, rather than evaluating its musical capabilities through musician feedback.

By conducting such an evaluation, we not only gathered insights on the *Tesremin* as an instrument but also received valuable feedback specific to this Tesla Coil. The visual appeal alone greatly intrigued both the musician and the audience, while the unique sound produced by the lightning bolts served as the "cherry on top" for participants, as they had never experienced anything like it before. This alone warrants its use.

However, the musician noted some drawbacks of the Tesla Coil. It struggles to accurately produce a wide range of frequencies, with particularly high (above 3000 Hz) and

low (below 150 Hz) notes sounding imperfect. Despite this limitation, the Tesla Coil remains a viable and intriguing musical instrument.

6.5 Reflecting on the aesthetics

Since the *Tesremin* is still in its prototype stage, its casing and overall presentation were kept minimalistic. The plastic box was primarily chosen to facilitate quick modifications, such as drilling additional holes if design changes were needed later. For prototyping purposes, this plastic container proved to be a practical choice while also offering an interesting design.

A similar practical solution could have been achieved by 3D printing a basic prototype. However, this approach would have incurred significantly higher costs and required more resources.

6.6 Future work

The most important issues to fix in future iterations is the noticeable delay. This might be done using other programs such as Pure Data or using different hardware components such as other distance sensors. Regardless, the key priority in this endeavor would be identifying the source of the delay.

Another possible addition is the previously talked about foot-operated button switch to stop the sensor input when pressed. This might allow players to further improve their *Tesremin* capabilities.

To further evaluate the *Tesremin* in real-world settings, a small live performance in front of a selected audience could be conducted. A more ambitious approach would be the creation of a Tesla Coil orchestra or band, where multiple similar instruments are played together.

To progress beyond the prototype stage, the *Tesremin* casing should also be improved. Instead of the current plastic exterior, a well-designed wooden enclosure or a custom 3D-printed container could be created.

Another potential addition could be a visual indication of distance, similar to the VR*emin* by Johnson et al. [6]. Since the *Tesremin* is a Digital Musical Instrument (DMI), there are numerous ways to enhance its playability and presentation. These improvements could range from a fully integrated VR setup to something as simple as a screen displaying the current hand distance, providing musicians with better control and feedback.

Finally, further iterations and testing should be carried out using a suitable Tesla Coil that supports amplitude shift, to fully realize the *Tesremin*'s potential and enhance its performance for live musical applications.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the *Tesremin*, a digital musical instrument combining a self-built Theremin using ultrasonic sensors and a Raspberry Pi, with a Tesla coil as the output device. The implementation was outlined in detail, along with the different approaches considered and the challenges each solution posed. A prototype was constructed for the purpose of housing the components and wiring. An

evaluation was conducted with a musician to assess the capabilities and appeal of the instrument. The musician exhibited excitement and curiosity toward the *Tesremin* and called it very appealing. The usability aspect shows great promise, as the instrument is easy to handle and comfortable to play, but still lacks fast response time and additional functionality such as a foot pedal to elevate it further. In conclusion, the *Tesremin* shows great potential and can be considered a successful DMI prototype. To exit its prototype state, additional improvements are needed.

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